

Assessing power-to-heat technologies for industrial electrification: A multi-criteria decision analysis approach

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ABSTRACT

Transitioning industrial heat systems from fossil fuels to electric-based solutions is crucial to mitigate climate change. This research identifies and evaluates various power-to-heat technologies, each technology contributes uniquely to the overarching goal of industrial electrification. Through a rigorous methodology involving categorisation based on technology readiness level (TRL), electrification stage, carbon emission per each kWh of heat delivery, energy efficiency, installation complexity, and life span, a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) is conducted to assess the performance of each technology. To validate the proposed ranking, the weighted sum method (WSM) was compared to the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). In addition to prioritizing each criterion, six scenarios were investigated using sensitivity analysis to determine the performance of each criterion and ranking of technologies using a scenario based weighting technique. The study indicates Heat Pump and Mechanical Vapor Recompression as the most dependable and high-performing technologies, continuously giving top marks and serving as the finest solutions for a wide range of applications. In contrast, Plasma Technology and Microwave and Radio frequency heaters are regarded as the least effective, with continuously low ratings, making them less desirable alternatives. By synthesizing the results and defining different scenarios, this detailed analysis provides decision-makers, industry stakeholders, and researchers with useful insights into the many alternatives for direct electrification of heat supply. Finally, the MCDA in this study is designed for current and future scenarios, allowing new technologies to be analyzed and ranked with the proposed algorithm.

Introduction

In the face of increasing concerns over climate change and the need to lower carbon emissions, industries worldwide are turning to novel strategies to decarbonise their operations [1]. Among these strategies, the direct electrification of heat supply emerges as a promising pathway towards achieving significant reductions in CO₂ emissions while enhancing energy efficiency and sustainability in industrial processes [2–4]. Industrial heat demand is projected to expand 16 % globally from 2023 to 2028 [5]. However, it is still heavily dependent on fossil fuels, emphasizing the critical need for a transition to cleaner and sustainable alternatives [6]. To achieve the required decarbonisation in industry, the reliance on fossil fuels must be replaced by energy generated from renewable energy sources [7]. Electricity generation is rapidly evolving toward cleaner energy, with countries like Ireland setting bold targets, such as achieving 70 % renewable energy in the electricity grid by 2030

[8]. Hence, industrial heat demand electrification can provide a simple and effective approach for decarbonising heat by immediately replacing fossil fuel-based processes with renewable electricity [9].

In achieving the objective of extending the transition through direct electrification of heat supply, identifying, and evaluating appropriate technologies is critical in influencing the trajectory toward industrial process sustainability and efficiency [10,11]. Several alternative technologies are available for electrifying an industrial site's heat supply, which indicates the use of electricity as the major energy source rather than the traditional method, which employs fossil fuels [12–14]. Heat pumps are the most popular of all the power-to-heat technologies; they apply the refrigeration cycles that move heat from cold to hot regions efficiently [15]. Heat pumps play a significant role in industrial applications by providing an efficient and sustainable solution for heat generation [16]. By utilizing renewable electricity, heat pumps significantly reduce carbon emissions compared to traditional fossil fuel-based

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systems [17]. They provide the flexibility to meet a wide range of heating and cooling needs in industries, making them adaptable for various processes. Their ability to recover and reuse waste heat further enhances their value, contributing to both cost savings and environmental sustainability in industrial operations [18]. Moreover, electric boilers appear as innovative solutions that contribute to the replacement of old fossil fuel-based systems [19]. They are the best example of direct electrification with a reduced number of steps. Electric boilers offer high efficiency, lower maintenance needs, and can be easily integrated into existing systems, making them ideal for industries aiming to decarbonise heat production [20].

Radio frequency and microwave heaters are two heat-delivery applications that use electromagnetic radiation [21]. Further advancements in radio frequency and microwave heaters provide fast and precise heating solutions for a wide range of industrial uses. These technologies employ electromagnetic radiation to improve energy efficiency and minimize processing times, hence furthering the goal of sustainable manufacturing methods [22].

Mechanical vapor recompression and infrared heaters are specific means of heat recovery and distribution, utilizing latent heat and infrared radiation, respectively [23]. These technologies not only improve energy efficiency but also provide personalized solutions for certain industrial processes, demonstrating the complex tactics required for successful electrification efforts [24,25]. The use of resistance and induction furnaces emphasizes the significance of accurate temperature control and consistent heating in material processing and thermal treatment [26]. By harnessing electrical resistance and electromagnetic induction, these furnaces enable efficient and sustainable practices while meeting the stringent demands of modern industrial applications [27]. Lastly, plasma technology and electric arc furnaces (EAFs) stand as pillars of efficiency in materials processing and alloy production [28]. Plasma technology harnesses the distinct characteristics of plasma for a myriad of industrial applications, while EAFs offer flexibility and reduced environmental impact compared to conventional methods [29].

A thorough examination of the suggested technologies is required to select the best electrification plan. MCDA is a particularly useful technique for simultaneously assessing various technologies across numerous dimensions [30]. MCDA's organised framework allows for systematic comparison, prioritisation, and selection of the optimal option while taking into account all important aspects [31,32]. MCDA is commonly used to enhance decision-making in a wide range of fields, including engineering, finance, and environmental management. The set of tools and techniques known as MCDA is meant to facilitate the decision-making process involving numerous criterion decision makers with each other, and be able to utilise distinct MCDA approaches to identify and evaluate the best options and alternatives based on detailed weights and performances of all relevant variables [33,34]. These methods include the technique of order priority by similarity of ideal solutions (TOPSIS), which prioritizes alternatives according to their proximity to ideal solutions, and the analytic hierarchy process (AHP), which uses pairwise comparisons to generate a priority scale [35–37]. Other techniques, such as Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT) [38,39], ELECTRE [40], and PROMETHEE [41,42], offers unique methods to combine and evaluate criteria, and ensure that every aspect of the decision problem is captured.

Despite the critical role of industrial electrification in achieving net-zero emissions, there is a noticeable gap in the literature regarding a comprehensive evaluation of power-to-heat technologies using a multi-criteria decision-making approach. Previous studies have often focused on individual technologies or assessed them based on limited criteria, lacking a holistic perspective. This fragmented approach hinders stakeholders from making informed decisions about which technologies offer the most effective pathways toward decarbonization. To bridge this gap, there is a need for a systematic and comparative analysis that integrates crucial criteria into a unified framework. By employing such an approach, it becomes possible to identify and prioritize technologies

that not only meet the technical requirements but also align with sustainability goals and practical implementation considerations.

Thus, this research will investigate and evaluate several technologies for direct electrification of heat supply in the industry to determine what are the most effective and efficient solutions to follow net zero plans. This study also aims to give policymakers, industry stakeholders, and academics insights and suggestions based on a unique MCDA of technology capabilities, technology readiness level, energy efficiency measures, emission reduction potentials, installation complexity and lifespan of technologies. By encouraging the development and integration of direct electrification technologies, industries may speed up their transition to a low-carbon future, contribute to global climate change mitigation efforts, and ensure a sustainable and prosperous future. Fig. 1 shows the main objectives and structure of this research, providing an overview of the systematic approach followed. It begins with identifying a range of power-to-heat technologies which are then categorized based on key criteria. The MCDA framework follows, comprising the selection and normalization of criteria, application of weighting methods, and aggregation techniques. The process concludes with results and discussion, where technologies are ranked based on scenario analysis to identify the most suitable options under various conditions.

Therefore, in Section 2, all criteria will be discussed to identify and categorize technologies based on each criterion required for MCDA. Section 3 will go into the major research framework of this study. First, the final categorisation of technologies based on Monte Carlo simulation for reducing uncertainties, min-max normalisation, and required inversion of criteria will be analyzed. Then, the proposed multi-criteria study will aim to identify the best industrial power-to-heat technology across many sectors. Section 4 will give a full result of the proposed MCDA to aid in determining the best alternatives. Also, a full discussion will be prepared and conducted by establishing related scenarios. Finally, Section 5 will address a concise summary of the research's results and discussion.

Criteria selection of technologies

The collective adoption and integration of power-to-heat technologies hold immense promise for reducing CO₂ emissions and enhancing industrial electrification. By leveraging renewable electricity and optimising energy utilisation, these technologies pave the way for a sustainable future characterized by reduced environmental impact and enhanced economic prosperity. The initial stage in determining the most suitable and currently available technology is to assess it in relation to other similar categories.

To facilitate this evaluation, after reviewing a wide range of research publications, six primary criteria were identified: Technology Readiness Level, Energy Efficiency, Installation Complexity, Electrification Stage, Carbon Emissions per kWh of heat delivery, and lifespan of each technology. The review focused on peer-reviewed journal articles, technical reports, and industrial case studies that specifically discuss the performance and application of power-to-heat technologies. The search criteria prioritized publications addressing industrial applications of electrification technologies, emphasizing sustainability, feasibility, and economic impacts. These criteria were selected based on their recurring importance in the reviewed literature and their relevance to the assessment of power-to-heat technologies. Each criterion is thoroughly explored in this study to provide a clear understanding of its role in the overall evaluation framework. These criteria are not entirely independent; for instance, higher TRL often coincides with lower Installation Complexity, while improved Energy Efficiency tends to reduce Carbon Emissions. These interdependencies can be leveraged to enhance the assessment framework, creating a more comprehensive and insightful evaluation. The interconnection of these criteria provides for a more accurate representation of a technology's real potential in industrial applications, ensuring that the evaluation captures not just isolated metrics, but the broader capability of each technology to contribute to

Fig. 1. Main structure of the research.

industrial electrification. Table 1 also shows the overall view of all technologies with their related values regarding all 6 criteria.

Electrification stage

Electrification is the process of integrating cutting-edge electrical technologies into a variety of industrial operations that have traditionally been powered by fossil fuels, such as manufacturing and heating [43]. Based on the stage of technological maturity, the grid integration capability, and the complexity of their integration into existing systems, there are three phases to the electrification of industrial processes. Each phase reflects distinct demands on grid infrastructure and highlights the evolving ability of the grid to accommodate new, electricity-based technologies seamlessly. Stage 1 consists of established technologies that are extensively used and have few integration-related difficulties. Stage 2 systems are more advanced and provide notable improvements, but they also come with higher infrastructure and specialized expertise requirements. While Stage 3 focuses heavily on cutting-edge technology with enormous potential for efficiency benefits, it also presents difficult integration hurdles and a great deal of technological uncertainty [44].

Stage 1 comprises electric boilers, heat pumps, mechanical vapor recompression and infrared heaters. These technologies are known for their use, in settings and their high efficiency. They are dependable, well-known and relatively easy to integrate into existing systems [45,46]. Phase 2 includes radio frequency heaters and microwave heaters. These advanced technologies are increasingly being implemented in processes. However, due to their nature and the inherent technological uncertainties involved their incorporation is more complex [47,48]. Resistance and induction furnaces are also categorized under Phase 2 [14]. Unlike Phase 1 technologies, adopting these technologies poses challenges even though they are established and widely utilized in metal processing. This is because effectively incorporating them requires knowledge and infrastructure. EAFs, while widely used in the steel industry, are considered to be at stage 3 because of the substantial effort needed for integration and their intricate nature. Similarly, plasma technology is also classified under stage 3 showcasing progress, with possibilities but facing considerable technological uncertainties and integration obstacles [49–51]. This classification provides a clear framework for understanding the readiness and potential challenges associated with integrating these technologies into industrial electrification efforts.

Energy Efficiency/COP

Energy efficiency and coefficient of performance (COP) in industries are of paramount importance as they directly impact economic performance and environmental sustainability [52]. Efficient energy use reduces operational costs, enhances competitiveness, and minimizes greenhouse gas emissions, thereby contributing to climate change

mitigation efforts. When evaluating power-to-heat technologies, energy efficiency is a key metric, defined as the ratio of useful energy output (E_{out}) to total electricity energy input (E_{in}):

$$\eta = \frac{E_{out}}{E_{in}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

This percentage-based metric is particularly relevant for direct energy conversion systems like electric boilers, and furnaces which directly convert electricity to heat. On the other hand, the COP is a key metric for assessing the efficiency of heat delivery systems, particularly heat pumps and MVR. It is defined as the ratio of useful heat output (Q_{out}) to electricity input (E_{in}):

$$COP = \frac{Q_{out}}{E_{in}} \quad (2)$$

Unlike efficiency, COP values are typically greater than 1 and depend on operating conditions, such as the temperature difference between the heat source and sink. By incorporating both efficiency and COP, this study ensures a comprehensive evaluation of power-to-heat technologies under various industrial conditions. When evaluating the energy efficiency of power-to-heat technologies, each technology demonstrates unique characteristics.

Heat pumps and MVR typically have COP's in excess of 3, the highest efficiency due to the use of the small amount of electrical energy for delivering heat from one source to another [53–55]. This COP means that for every 1 kWh of electrical energy consumed, they can output more than 3 kWh of heat. Electric boilers are relatively straightforward, converting electrical energy directly into heat with an efficiency of nearly 100% [56]. Roughly 70–90% of electricity is converted into heat by infrared heaters through radiation. This kind of heating helps to reduce the energy losses that might have been experienced; hence it is valuable in targeted heating for industrial purposes [57–59].

On the other hand, microwave heaters and radio frequency heaters heat efficiently by interacting directly with materials' molecules. Their efficiency varies between 60% and 90% depending on the material and use case. These technologies are effective in processes that require quick as well as even heating such as drying or curing [48,60].

The efficiency of induction furnaces ranges between 50% and 95%, depending on application [61,62]. The direct heating mechanism reduces energy losses during metal melting as well as heat treatment. The efficiency of resistance furnaces is the same as induction ones in terms of energy conversion, but their working principle is based on the conversion of electrical energy into heat through resistive elements [51]. High-temperature applications that require accurate temperature control often employ resistance furnaces. EAFs have an efficiency of about 65–85% and are mostly used in the steel industry. These furnaces use electric arcs to melt scrap metal thereby converting a significant part of the electrical power to thermal one, although there are radiant heat and off-gas losses [63,64].

Finally, plasma technology is an example where ionized gases generate extremely high temperatures with efficiencies ranging from 60–

90 %. Plasma heaters serve specific purposes like material processing and waste treatment that need high temperatures under controlled conditions to be accomplished [65]. Collectively, these power-to-heat technologies demonstrate varying levels of electricity consumption efficiency, each contributing to enhanced energy efficiency in industrial applications based on their specific operational principles and applications [66]. By leveraging these technologies, industries can achieve significant energy savings, reduce operational costs, and minimize their environmental impact.

Technology readiness level

A systematic way to describe a technology's readiness for commercialisation is to use the Technology Readiness Level (TRL), which ranges from 1 (beginning lab development) to 9 (complete commercial development). TRLs are explained in further detail below, along with each technology's score. Note that the TRL scale has multiple implications and that different organisations use various versions of it. The TRLs in this research have been determined using the Horizon 2020 TRL scale [67].

Heat pumps, Mechanical Vapor Recompression (MVR) systems, electric boilers, resistance furnaces, infrared heaters, induction furnaces, and EAFs are all at TRL 9, indicating full maturity and widespread adoption in industrial applications [68,69]. Heat pumps and electric boilers are extensively used across residential, commercial, and industrial sectors, playing a crucial role in sustainable energy systems. MVR, infrared heaters, and resistance furnaces are well-established in industrial heat treatment processes, known for their technological advances, energy efficiency, and environmental benefits. Induction furnaces and EAFs are effective for metal melting and heat treatment processes due to their extensive industrial use and efficiency.

Microwave heaters, radio frequency heaters, and plasma technology are at TRL 7. Microwave heaters are applied in specialized industrial functions and are under advanced development stages achieving significant adoption in industrial contexts. Radio frequency heaters are already at the advanced development stage, thanks to the continually evolving technological capabilities behind the broadening industrial use [70]. Plasma is a technology used in industry, the variety of applications are at different levels of maturity, but with the increasing use of this technology, the situation is also sustainable for industrial processes [68]. All these evaluations together provide a complete overview of TRLs of industries' different technologies, indicating the presence and the potential of these processes in the future applications of industry.

Installation complexity

The implementation intensity of industrial technologies defines how intricate it is to include a particular technology into the current framework. Some of the issues that make the process complicated include specialized equipment, new infrastructures put in place, specialized human resources, and time to be taken in installation among others [71]. This section compares the installation ease of different industrial heating technologies and discusses each of them briefly.

When compared to traditional fuel-based solutions, heat pumps and electric boilers are comparatively simple to install. They reduce the need for the complicated fuel storage, handling, and ventilation systems seen in fossil fuel systems [72]. However, they do need adequate integration with existing heating systems and, in the case of heat pumps, additional space for outside equipment [73]. MVR adds complexity and therefore raises costs. MVR systems, unlike heat pumps, require additional pipes and controls for the waste heat-carrying circuit and should therefore, be installed by experts. Microwave, radio frequency and induction heaters are rather sophisticated pieces of equipment used in industries [74,75]. They require personnel with the right experience when it comes to installation as well as observing certain safety measures. The Resistance furnaces are of different levels of complexity. Small units are relatively

easy to understand as they are like electrical ovens. But large furnaces used in industries call for elaborate structures and they are a preserve for skilled technicians [76]. EAFs and plasma technology are at the highest level of the mentioned types of furnaces [77,78]. These highly dangerous systems require extensive engineering, safety measures, and highly trained professionals for installation.

Carbon emission per kWh

One of the most significant tasks in making industries sustainable is reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Carbon emissions per kilowatt-hour engaged in the process of production are the determining factors for environmental pollution. The carbon emissions of various industrial technologies are assessed in this section according to their efficiency values. A precise value is needed to calculate the total CO₂ emissions associated with delivering 1 kWh of energy. In this study, the Irish grid carbon emission is taken into consideration, with a value of 0.254 kg/kWh electricity generation [79]. Considering the efficiency factor of each technology, heat delivery can be achieved with:

$$E_{output} = E_{elec} \times \eta \quad (3)$$

where η is the efficiency of each technology, and E_{elec} is the required energy of heat delivery.

Then, the total energy required to deliver heat can be calculated as:

$$E_{elec} = \frac{E_{output}}{\eta} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the required energy for delivering 1kWh of heat delivery can be calculated as below:

$$E_{elec} = \frac{1}{\eta} \quad (5)$$

The CO₂ emission factor of the grid electricity, total carbon emission for 1kWh of heat delivery can be achieved in Eq. (3):

$$F_{elec(total)} = E_{elec} \times f_{elec} \quad (6)$$

where f_{elec} is the grid electricity carbon emission factor. The result of the calculation for all technologies can be found in Table 1.

Lifespan

The lifecycle of heat delivery technologies is a critical factor for industries aiming to balance long-term cost-efficiency with operational reliability. Technologies with a longer life span require fewer replacements, reducing the capital expenditure over time and minimizing the environmental impact of manufacturing after the life cycle of the equipment [80]. Moreover, durability ensures stable system performance, reducing downtime and operational disruptions. The life span of heat delivery equipment is determined by a variety of factors, including daily usage, regular maintenance, temperature range, different models and manufacturers, etc. This section compiles an overview of technology lifespans based on the most recent research.

Electric boilers, infrared heaters, resistance furnaces, and plasma technologies have an average lifespan of 20 years [81,82]. Electric boilers have a basic design with few moving parts, needing little care beyond occasional cleaning and electrode replacement. Infrared heaters, which are frequently used for focused heating, deteriorate more quickly in dusty or corrosive conditions, necessitating regular inspection. Resistance furnaces, with their precise temperature control capabilities, rely primarily on the durability of heating elements and insulation, which must be updated on a regular basis to ensure long-lasting performance. Plasma technology, which is well-known for its ability to handle high-temperature procedures, has a limited lifespan due to the wear of its torches and electrodes, which must be replaced on a regular basis under heavy use.

Microwave and radio frequency heaters generally last at most 10 years, depending on the operating circumstances [83]. The lifespan of microwave heaters is strongly dependent on the upkeep of magnetrons and electronic controllers, both of which are prone to wear in harsh industrial conditions [84]. Similarly, radio frequency heaters used for selective heating applications require regular service of power sources and electronic circuits in order to reach their full life cycle. Both methods benefit from regulated operating conditions and regular inspections to prevent component failures.

Heat pumps and mechanical vapor recompression systems have a longer operational lifespan of 25 years [85]. Heat pumps, which are known for their energy efficiency and versatility, require frequent maintenance of compressors, refrigerants, and heat exchangers to ensure their longevity. Similarly, MVR systems, effective in reusing heat, benefit from robust compressors and well-maintained piping networks, which ensure consistent performance and a long life span.

The most durable technologies on the list are induction and EAFs, which have a lifespan of up to 30 years. Induction furnaces, which are widely used in metal melting and heat treatment, rely on the integrity of refractory linings and power electronics, both of which require regular maintenance to avoid operational failures [86]. EAFs, a steel industry staple, accomplish their long life by meticulous maintenance of electrodes, refractory linings, and cooling systems that are subjected to extreme working conditions.

Table 1 depicts an overall overview of all described criteria and discussed technologies achieved from references. All the values presented in the table are derived from an extensive review of existing literature, including peer-reviewed journal articles, technical reports, and industrial case studies. These values have been carefully extracted from credible sources to ensure accuracy and relevance. The selection process involved identifying key data points reported in the literature that align with the focus of this study.

Research methodology

Following the implementation of decarbonisation and net zero plans, the fundamental objective of this research is to help stakeholders in industrial sectors so that they can make a more informed decision regarding the integration of power to heat technologies. The categorisation of technologies and the performance of a customized multi-criteria analysis will be the primary objectives of this section, which comprises the study framework. Within the context of the categorisation of technologies, 6 criteria will be finalized for each of the power-to-heat technologies, and a comprehensive discussion will be included in the MCDA.

Categorizing technologies

The standard MCDA consists of three main processes, the first of which is normalisation to ensure that all criterion values are on the same scale. Following that, each criterion's weighting must be applied in

Table 1

Overall view of technology categorisation.

Technology	Electrification stages	Efficiency	TRL (Technology maturity)	Installation complexity	CO ₂ emission (1kWh of heat)	Lifespan	References
Electric boilers	1	95–99 %	9	low	0.261	20	[45,56,69,72,81]
Mechanical vapor recompression	1	3.25	9	Medium	0.078	25	[46,54,69,85]
Heat pump	1	3	9	Low	0.084	25	[45,53,69,72,85]
Infrared heaters	1	70–90 %	9	low	0.319	20	[57,59,81,82]
Microwave heaters	2	60–90 %	7	High	0.340	10	[48,60,70,83,84]
Radio frequency heaters	2	60–90 %	7	High	0.339	10	[47,70,74,83]
Induction furnace	2	50–95 %	9	High	0.352	30	[14,61,75,86]
Resistance furnace	2	50–95 %	9	High	0.351	20	[14,51,69,77,82]
Electric arc furnace	3	65–85 %	9	Very high	0.339	30	[51,63,64,77,86]
Plasma technology	3	60–90 %	7	Very high	0.338	20	[49,65,66,68,78,82]

order to prioritize criteria based on subjective or objective weighting suggestions. The final step is to use the selected aggregation technique to examine all criteria and generate a list of technologies based on their rankings. The categorisation of technologies has an important impact on the MCDA result as the decision analysis relies on the accuracy of the values in the proposed table. Therefore, there are some adjustments and presets to put the values on the same scale and apply comparison, inversion of some categories, etc. Fig. 2 illustrates the overall process for categorizing technologies in a structured and systematic manner as a part of MCDA.

The process begins with defining the data, which involves identifying the required inputs and parameters for the analysis. Next, the data is converted into a suitable data frame, to facilitate subsequent steps. Handling data is crucial at this stage to ensure that incomplete information does not affect the reliability of the analysis. In cases where uncertain values are present, a Monte Carlo simulation is applied to account for variability, generating a range of possible outcomes for greater robustness.

After addressing uncertainties, the process evaluates whether any criteria require inversion. This step is particularly important for criteria where lower values are preferable, such as carbon emission. If inversion is necessary, the relevant categories are adjusted accordingly. Once all criteria are finalized, the technologies are categorized and normalized to ensure consistency across the dataset. This structured approach enables an accurate evaluation of the technologies, providing a solid foundation for further analysis.

Monte Carlo simulation

Monte Carlo simulation is a statistical technique that allows for the modeling of complex systems and the estimation of their behavior through the use of random sampling since it derives numerical conclusions, it is helpful in scenarios where analytical solutions are impractical or unattainable. The Monte Carlo simulation employed in this study can effectively reduce the uncertainty surrounding the efficiency category.

First, the efficiency range (E_{low} and E_{high}) for each entity is defined. Using a uniform distribution, random samples are generated within this range. A uniform distribution is characterized by the property that all outcomes are equally likely within the specified range [E_{low}, E_{high}]. The probability density function (PDF) for a uniform distribution can be given as:

$$f(X) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{E_{high} - E_{low}} & \text{for } E_{low} \leq X \leq E_{high} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

In the Monte Carlo simulation, random samples X_j are generated from this uniform distribution:

$$X_j = \text{Uniform}(E_{low}, E_{high}) \quad (8)$$

Where j ranges from 1 to N , the number of samples. After generating random samples, the mean efficiency is calculated to represent the expected efficiency considering the inherent viability. The final efficiency

Fig. 2. Overall process of categorization.

can be achieved using the formula:

$$E = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^n X_j \tag{9}$$

where N is the total number of samples. This calculation provides a single, averaged efficiency value derived from the multiple random samples, capturing the variability and uncertainty in the efficiency percentages. This method guarantees that the range and distribution of potential efficiencies are appropriately reflected in the fixed mean efficiency estimate that is utilized in later assessments.

Inversion of criteria

In multi-criteria decision analysis often, it is needed to invert some criteria so that all criteria are comparable and on the same scale. This is necessary when some criteria imply that higher is worse. In the proposed category, electrification stage, installation complexity and CO₂ emission categories require to be inverted so that lower is better. Once it has identified those criteria, then it needs to find the maximum value for each criterion in the dataset. This maximum value will be the reference point for the inversion. The maximum value C_{max} is identified using the formula:

$$C_{max} = \max(\{C_{i1}, C_{i2}, \dots, C_{in}\}) \tag{10}$$

With this maximum value determined, the inversion calculation for each value C_i in the criterion is performed using the formula:

$$InvertedC_i = C_{max} + 1 - C_i \tag{11}$$

This formula effectively reverses the scale of the criterion, ensuring that higher original values, which indicate worse performance, are transformed into lower values. This inversion ensures that all criteria are aligned such that lower values are universally better, facilitating a consistent and meaningful aggregation of the criteria.

Normalisation of criteria

Normalisation is a data preprocessing technique to scale features in a dataset to the same level. This is necessary in many multi-criteria analyses and decision-making processes to prevent features with the larger scale from dominating the model. One of the most common ways to do normalisation is min-max normalisation. Min-max normalisation scales data within a range [0, 1]. This will adjust the values of features so that all values are within the same range, preserve the relationship between the values and prevent one feature from dominating due to its scale. To perform min-max normalisation, the first step is to identify the minimum and maximum values of the feature to be normalized. Using these values, each data point within the feature is then transformed using the min-max normalisation formula. The formula for min-max normalisation can be defined as:

$$X_{norm} = \frac{X - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}} \tag{12}$$

Where X represents the original value, X_{min} is the minimum available value, and the X_{max} represents the maximum value of the feature. This method preserves the relative relationships between the original data points, making it particularly suitable when these relationships are important.

Weighting application

The weighting of criteria is a crucial factor in the process of making a decision as it helps in determining the relative importance of each factor which will be considered. In terms of power-to-heat technologies, a proper weighting of the factors is necessary in order to make the evaluation process truly reflect the priorities of the decision-makers. Techniques of weighing can be generally divided into subjective and objective approaches. The subjective weighting is achieved by the ex-

pert's judgment or the stakeholder's input which allocates the weights corresponding to the importance that they perceive while articulating their favorable priorities and values. Objective weighting, conversely, is statistical which acquires weights through data's inherent qualities with the application of mathematical or statistical methods. Therefore, this study is aimed at a subjective method that would involve industry-specific criteria to reflect a more realistic analysis in comparison with objective methods. The initial weighting in this analysis is built on the basis of the equal weighting method. This strategy involves allocating each weight to the respective criterion uniformly so that the total sum of the weights equals 1. If there are n criteria, the weight w_j for each criterion j is calculated as:

$$w_j = \frac{1}{n} \quad (13)$$

This ensures that:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1 \quad (14)$$

Aggregation methods

In this study, both the WSM and the TOPSIS were employed within the MCDA framework to evaluate the power-to-heat technologies. WSM was chosen for its simplicity and ease of implementation, allowing for direct aggregation of weighted criteria scores and straightforward interpretation of results. TOPSIS was selected for its ability to consider the relative distance of each technology from an ideal solution, effectively capturing trade-offs among multiple criteria. Utilizing both methods provides a comprehensive evaluation and enhances the robustness of the analysis by cross-validating the findings from different analytical perspectives.

Weighted sum method

The Weighted Sum Method (WSM) is a widely used approach in MCDA to evaluate and rank a set of alternatives based on multiple criteria by means of specificity. In this method, one main advantage is that a specific score is calculated related to a particular issue and the others are consolidated into it and one number is used to express the overall performance, which means that it simplifies the process and only uses one score for each alternative to give a general evaluation of that particular alternative.

Mathematically, the weighted sum for an alternative i is calculated using the formula:

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \times x_{ij} \quad (15)$$

where S_i represents the weighted sum for alternative i , w_j is the weight assigned to the criterion j , x_{ij} is the score of alternatives i for criterion j , and n is the total number of criteria. After calculating the weighted sum for each alternative, these alternatives are ranked based on their S_i values. The alternative with the highest weighted sum is considered the best option according to the weighted criteria.

TOPSIS

The TOPSIS is a widely used MCDA method for ranking and selecting a predetermined number of alternatives by distance measurement. The basic idea behind TOPSIS is that solutions will be found from limited alternatives. This method assumes that each criterion is either monotonically increasing or decreasing, allowing the criteria to be maximised or minimized. TOPSIS starts by converting values into a similar metric using a general decision matrix. Normalisation accomplishes this by guaranteeing that all criteria values range between 0 and 1. A weighted generalized decision matrix is produced in the following stage. The relative weight of each criterion in the decision-making process is indicated by multiplying its normalized value by itself. The formula for the weighted normalized value v_{ij} is given by:

$$v_{ij} = w_j + r_{ij} \quad (16)$$

where w_j is the weight of the criterion j and r_{ij} is the normalized value of the criterion j for alternative i . Subsequently, TOPSIS determines the ideal and negative-ideal solutions. The ideal solution A^+ consists of the maximum values for each criterion. For example, the ideal solution might include the highest possible energy efficiency, TRL, and minimum CO₂ emission. Conversely, the negative-ideal solution A^- consists of the worst possible performance values for each criterion. The formulas are as follows:

$$A^+ = \{\max(v_{ij})|j \in \text{criteriatomaximise}, \min(v_{ij})|j \in \text{criteriatominimize}\} \quad (17)$$

$$A^- = \{\min(v_{ij})|j \in \text{criteriatomaximise}, \max(v_{ij})|j \in \text{criteriatominimize}\} \quad (18)$$

Next, the separation measures are calculated to determine the distance of each alternative from the ideal and negative-ideal solutions. The Euclidean distance is commonly used, resulting in the separation from the ideal solution S_i^+ and the separation from the negative-ideal solution S_i^- :

$$S_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - A_j^+)^2} \quad (19)$$

$$S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - A_j^-)^2} \quad (20)$$

The relative closeness to the ideal solution is then calculated for each alternative. This measure indicates how close each alternative is to the ideal solution, relative to the negative-ideal solution. The relative closeness C_i^* is defined as:

$$C_i^* = \frac{S_i^-}{S_i^+ + S_i^-} \quad (21)$$

where $0 \leq C_i^* \leq 1$. Higher C_i^* values indicate a closer proximity to the ideal solution. The alternatives are then ranked based on their relative closeness values, with higher values indicating better performance. This ranking provides decision-makers with a clear and quantifiable method to evaluate and select the best alternative from a set of options.

Results and discussion

The methodology section detailed the systematic approach taken to evaluate the alternatives, including the selection and justification of criteria, the application of the WSM for aggregation, and the assignment of weights based on industry relevance and expert input. Following the methodology, the results section presents the findings from the analysis conducted in this study, offering a detailed examination of the data and outcomes derived from the applied methodologies. This section systematically evaluates the performance of the alternatives under consideration, based on the criteria and weighting schemes established earlier. By interpreting the results, we aim to provide insights into the relative effectiveness of each alternative, identify the most promising options, and discuss any significant trends or patterns that emerged during the analysis. In addition to presenting the primary findings, this section also includes a scenario analysis to explore how different assumptions, such as changes in weighting schemes impact the results. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of the robustness of the conclusions and provides insights into how different conditions might influence the performance of the alternatives. Applying the proposed methods for the primary table, [Table 2](#). Represents the final categorisation of all technologies.

To prepare the data for the multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA), a systematic process was followed, aligning with the methodology illustrated in [Fig. 2](#). This process involved several key steps: data definition, handling uncertainties, inversion of certain criteria, and normalization

Table 2
Final categorisation of all technologies.

Technology	Electrification stages	Efficiency	TRL (Technological maturity)	Installation complexity	CO ₂ emission (1 kWh of heat)	Lifespan
Electric boilers	1	0.298	1	1	0.330	0.5
Mechanical vapor recompression	1	1	1	0.66	1	0.75
Heat pump	1	0.923	1	1	0.976	0.75
Infrared heaters	1	0.244	1	1	0.121	0.5
Microwave heaters	0.5	0.229	0	0.33	0.043	0
Radio frequency heaters	0.5	0.230	0	0.33	0.046	0
Induction furnace	0.5	0.221	1	0.33	0	1
Resistance furnace	0.5	0.222	1	0.33	0.002	0.5
Electric arc furnace	0	0.230	1	0	0.048	1
Plasma technology	0	0.231	0	0	0.051	0.5

of all criteria values. Initially, data from various sources were compiled into a structured format, ensuring consistency in units and measurement scales. For criteria with uncertain or variable values, such as efficiency, Monte Carlo simulation was employed to account for variability and uncertainty. This statistical technique generated representative mean values for each technology by averaging numerous random samples within the specified ranges.

Certain criteria, such as CO₂ emissions per kWh of heat delivered, installation complexity, and electrification stage, have lower values indicating better performance. To align all criteria so that higher values consistently represent better performance, these values were inverted by subtracting each value from the maximum value observed in that criterion. Finally, to ensure all criteria are on a comparable scale, min–max normalization was applied to all criteria values. This involved scaling the values between 0 and 1.

For example, to illustrate the data processing and normalization steps for the installation complexity criterion, consider the case of Electric Boilers. The installation complexity levels were initially described qualitatively (Low, Medium, High, Very High) and were converted into numerical values for analysis: 'Low' was assigned a value of 1, 'Medium' a value of 2, 'High' a value of 3, and 'Very High' a value of 4. Since lower installation complexity is preferable, inversion was necessary to align this criterion with others where higher values indicate better performance. This inversion was performed by subtracting each technology's installation complexity value from the maximum value (which is 4) and adding the minimum value (which is 1). For Electric Boilers, with an original value of 1, the inverted value regarding eq. (11) can be achieved as below:

$$\text{Inverted}C_i = (4 - 1) + 1 = 4 \quad (22)$$

This ensures that the inverted values range from 1 (least preferred) to 4 (most preferred), matching the original scale but with the desirability direction reversed.

Next, min–max normalization was applied regarding eq. (12) to scale the inverted values between 0 and 1. The minimum inverted value across all technologies is 1 (corresponding to 'Very High' complexity), and the maximum is 4 (corresponding to 'Low' complexity). The normalized installation complexity for Electric Boilers is calculated as:

$$X_{\text{norm}} = \frac{4 - 1}{4 - 1} = 1 \quad (23)$$

This normalized value of 1 indicates the best performance in this criterion and is presented in Table 2 under the "Installation Complexity" column for Electric Boilers. This example demonstrates how the qualitative assessments were transformed into quantitative, normalized values suitable for comparison and analysis in the multi-criteria decision framework. Similarly, the other criteria were processed using the same inversion and normalization steps to ensure all values are comparable on a scale from 0 to 1.

Weighted sum method analysis

The Weighted Sum Analysis graph visually represents the aggregated performance of various power-to-heat technologies across multiple criteria. Each technology is evaluated by summing the weighted values of these criteria, allowing for a comparative analysis of their overall effectiveness. To maintain objectivity and avoid bias towards any particular criterion, an equal weighting method is employed. This approach assigns the same level of importance to each criterion, reflecting a scenario where all factors are considered equally significant in the evaluation process. Given that there are six criteria, regarding eq.13, the weight assigned to each criterion is calculated as follows:

$$w_j = \frac{1}{6} \approx 0.1667 \text{ for } j = 1, 2, \dots, 6 \quad (24)$$

The stacked bar chart in Fig. 3 provides a clear depiction of how each technology performs relative to others, highlighting both the individual contributions of each criterion and the total weighted score.

As it is clear in the graph, heat pump technology is the top-ranked alternative in the analysis, having the highest total weighted score. This is partially due to its outstanding performance in most categories. The high CO₂ emissions score shows that it is both efficient and ecologically beneficial, making it an excellent candidate for broad use in power-to-heat applications. MVR follows closely after, with a comparable high total score. It outperforms the heat pump in terms of efficiency and CO₂ emissions, but its somewhat lower installation difficulty results in a second-place rating. Nonetheless, it remains a very competitive technology, especially when efficiency is a top priority.

Electric boilers and infrared heaters are the next two technologies on the list. They score highly in the electrification phases, TRL, and installation complexity, indicating their suitability for integration and simplicity of use. However, their low efficiency and CO₂ emission levels restrict their overall rating. These technologies have a balanced approach, but their somewhat lower efficiency may make them less appealing in situations when energy savings are critical.

Microwave heaters, radio frequency heaters, induction furnaces, and resistance furnaces are categorized as mid-range in this analysis. These technologies often have lower overall ratings because of their high installation complexity and CO₂ emissions, indicating that they are inefficient for utilisation when compared to heat pumps and MVR. EAFs and plasma technologies rank at the bottom of the list, due to their low electrification stages and installation complexity which means these technologies are not suitable for installation in heat applications.

TOPSIS analysis

The WSM is widely used due to its simplicity and ease of interpretation, making it highly practical for decision-makers in many scenarios. While it assumes that poor performance in one criterion can be offset by better performance in another, this compensatory behavior may not always align with specific decision-making needs. To explore this

Fig. 3. WSM visualisation of criteria.

further, the TOPSIS method is applied as a comparative analysis. TOPSIS is a more complex approach, taking into account both the ideal and worst-case possibilities for each criterion, guaranteeing that the optimal option is closest to the ideal solution while being farthest from the worst. This strategy better balances the trade-offs across criteria, lowering the influence of extreme values and offering a more robust framework for

decision-making in complicated circumstances. In this approach, the findings will be analyzed with TOPSIS to validate the suggested methodology.

Fig. 4 illustrates both the negative and ideal distances of each technology. The combined separation graph provides a visual comparison of how each technology distances itself from both the ideal and negative-

Fig. 4. Combined separation distance graph (Mix of Negative and Positive).

ideal solutions in the TOPSIS analysis. The blue bars represent the separation distance from the ideal solution, where smaller values indicate closer proximity to the ideal scenario. Conversely, the red bars show the separation from the negative-ideal solution, with larger values signifying greater distance from the worst-case scenario. Comparing these two sets of bars for each technology allows an individual to immediately determine which technologies are well-balanced, with a closer alignment to the ideal and a large distance from the negative ideal.

To derive the negative and ideal distances in the TOPSIS analysis, each technology's performance across all criteria is first normalized to ensure comparability. The ideal solution is constructed by selecting the best normalized value for each criterion, representing the most favorable performance achievable. Conversely, the negative-ideal solution comprises the worst normalized values for each criterion, reflecting the least desirable performance. The distances between each technology and these ideal and negative-ideal solutions are then calculated using the Euclidean distance formula. For example, considering the Lifespan criterion for the Resistance Furnace technology, the normalized lifespan value for the Resistance Furnace is 0.5. The ideal lifespan value is 1.0 (the highest normalized lifespan among all technologies), and the negative ideal lifespan value is 0.0 (the lowest normalized lifespan). The distance from the ideal solution is calculated as the difference between the Resistance Furnace's normalized value and the ideal value, resulting in a distance of 0.5. Similarly, the distance from the negative-ideal solution is the difference between its normalized value and the negative-ideal value, also 0.5. These distances indicate that the Resistance Furnace is equidistant from both the best and worst scenarios for the Lifespan criterion. After determining the separation distances, it is essential to assess the relative proximity to the optimal solution. Fig. 5 depicts the relative closeness of each technology, demonstrating how well they balance proximity to both the ideal and negative-ideal circumstances. This graph offers a concise review of each technology's overall performance, with higher bars indicating more alignment with the targeted goals. By applying this method across all criteria and technologies, the TOPSIS analysis quantifies each technology's relative closeness to the ideal solution. This approach allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the technologies, balancing their performance across multiple criteria and aiding in the decision-making process.

Technologies with greater relative closeness scores, such as the Heat Pump and MVR, achieve an optimal balance across the analysed criteria,

bringing them closer to the ideal solution and further away from the negative ideal one. Electric boilers and infrared heaters show great alignment with the targeted goals, making them promising alternatives for power-to-heat utilisation in industries. In contrast, technologies with lower relative proximity ratings, such as Plasma Technology and EAFs, identify areas where performance enhancements might be made to improve overall alignment with optimal industrial integrations.

Comparison of proposed WSM vs TOPSIS

Upon comparing the results obtained from the TOPSIS analysis and WSM, it becomes evident that the rankings of technologies are mostly consistent across both techniques with minor differences in the rankings of various technologies. The similarity in rankings validates the robustness of both methodologies, demonstrating that they yield comparable insights despite their different approaches to multi-criteria decision-making. This alignment not only reinforces the reliability of the rankings but also serves as a validation of the overall methodology employed in this research. The consistency between TOPSIS and WSM confirms that the criteria weights and normalisation processes were appropriately calibrated, ensuring that the evaluation of each technology accurately reflects its performance across all relevant dimensions. Fig. 6 shows the comparison between these two models.

By comparing the ranking results of WSM and TOPSIS, it can be demonstrated that WSM remains an effective and reliable method for this study's objectives, supporting its applicability even in more nuanced decision-making scenarios.

Scenario analysis

In the context of MCDA, scenario analysis is an important component of sensitivity analysis, which is used to evaluate the resilience and reliability of the decision-making process. Scenario analysis, which systematically varies the weights allocated to various criteria, gives insights into how changes in priority impact the overall ranking of options. This study uses scenario analysis to investigate the influence of prioritizing different criteria on the ranking of various power-to-heat technologies. Each scenario is created by giving a dominating weight to one criterion while weighing the remaining factors equally.

The weighting scheme in the scenario analysis is designed to reflect

Fig. 5. Relative closeness of technologies to the ideal solution.

Fig. 6. Comparison between TOPSIS vs WSM.

situations where decision-makers prioritize one specific criterion while still considering the others. Assigning a weight of 0.4 to the prioritized criterion ensures it has the most significant influence on the overall ranking, reflecting its heightened importance in that scenario. Meanwhile, distributing the remaining 0.6 equally (0.12 each) among the other five criteria maintains a balanced evaluation framework, ensuring they still contribute meaningfully to the decision but with less emphasis. This approach simulates real-world decision-making where a single factor such as Lifespan, Installation Complexity, or CO₂ emission might dominate considerations due to specific project or policy goals, while other factors remain relevant but secondary. By systematically varying the prioritization, this method captures the sensitivity of technology rankings to changing priorities, enabling stakeholders to understand how results align with diverse strategic preferences. Fig. 7 illustrates the proposed scenario analysis steps.

This rigorous weighting helps to determine which technologies are regularly scored highly and which are more affected by variations in criteria focus. The scenario analysis is provided in six sections, each representing a specific situation where a different criterion is given importance to assess the impact of prioritizing different criteria on the ranking of power-to-heat technologies. Fig. 8 illustrates the outcome of prioritizing each category and conducting scenario analysis based on each criterion.

The electrification of industrial processes offers sustainable opportunities for reducing carbon footprints and enhancing energy efficiency since it shows how industries can reduce dependency on fossil fuels with electricity as their major energy source. Technologies with greater electrification stages are more advanced and developed in integrating electricity for heat generation, which makes such technologies especially important in the context of the global energy transition to more sustainable and low-carbon energy systems. Compared to equal weighting, when prioritizing the electrification stage, heat pumps lead the ranking with a value of 0.958, closely followed by MVR, which scores 0.929. Electric boilers and infrared heaters perform reasonably well, with scores of 0.775 and 0.744, respectively. However, plasma technology and microwave heaters fall behind, with scores of 0.094 and 0.272, indicating their limited suitability for electrified systems.

Efficiency is an important parameter in assessing power-to-heat technologies since it directly evaluates the extent to which technology turns energy into practical heat. Higher efficiency means less energy is wasted during the conversion process, making the technology more cost-effective while also contributing to sustainability goals. Prioritizing efficiency/COP, heat pumps and MVR both excel with high efficiency ratings of 0.936 and 0.929. Electric boilers and infrared heaters demonstrate moderate efficiency, scoring 0.579 and 0.532, respectively. Meanwhile, microwave heaters and plasma technology are less efficient, with values of 0.196 and 0.159, pointing to higher energy losses in their operation.

When selecting technologies for energy systems, those with higher TRLs are often chosen since they carry fewer risks and are more likely to fulfill performance objectives. Giving priority to TRL, heat pumps and

MVR again dominate, each scoring 0.958 and 0.929, reflecting their high level of technological maturity and real-world implementation. Electric boilers and infrared heaters follow with values of 0.775 and 0.744, respectively, while microwave and radio frequency heaters and plasma technologies lag with lower TRL scores of 0.132 and 0.094, indicating they are still in developmental stages.

Technologies with lower installation complexity tend to be preferred since they can potentially be installed faster and with fewer modifications to the existing system, lowering total implementation costs and potential downtime. Prioritizing installation complexity in technology selection ensures that the chosen solutions are not only effective but also practicable and cost-effective to implement. In this way, heat pumps stand out with a score of 0.958, followed by MVR at 0.834 and electric boilers at 0.775, showing their relative ease of installation. Infrared heaters also perform well at 0.744, whereas plasma technology scores much lower at 0.094, respectively, reflecting the challenges associated with their installation.

In terms of carbon reduction scenario, CO₂ emission reduction in technology selection promises that the chosen solutions contribute to a decrease in greenhouse gas emissions and align with environmental sustainability goals. In the case when CO₂ reduction is highlighted, heat pumps and MVR again prove their effectiveness, each achieving a top score of 0.951 and 0.929. Electric boilers and infrared heaters also contribute to emission reductions, with mid range values of 0.585 and 0.494. However, plasma technology scores the lowest in this category, at 0.108, indicating higher levels of carbon emissions compared to other technologies.

Finally, lifespan is a critical criterion in evaluating power-to-heat technologies, as it determines the longevity and reliability of the system, impacting overall lifecycle costs and sustainability. Technologies with longer lifespans offer greater long-term value and reduce the need for frequent replacements, thereby minimizing environmental impacts. When prioritizing lifespan, heat pumps and MVR achieve top scores of 0.888 and 0.859, indicating their durability and extended operational periods. Electric boilers and induction furnaces maintain respectable scores of 0.635 and 0.646, respectively. In contrast, radio and microwave frequency receive lower lifespan scores of 0.132, suggesting shorter operational lifespans and higher maintenance requirements.

Fig. 9 provides a comprehensive overview of how each technology performs across all six scenarios, with each scenario prioritizing a different criterion.

The heat pump consistently ranks as the best-performing technology in every scenario, demonstrating its adaptability and robustness. This steady performance demonstrates its dependability and versatility, making it appropriate for a variety of industrial applications. Similarly, MVR and electric boilers are typically ranked second and third which perform nearly as well as the heat pump demonstrating their efficacy and dependability. On the other hand, plasma technology and EAFs frequently perform inadequately across all parameters. Their failure to achieve crucial performance makes them less appealing.

However, middle-ranking technologies such as infrared, microwave

Fig. 7. Scenario analysis proposed method.

and radio frequency heaters as well as induction and resistance furnaces provide a more mixed picture. Notably, the rankings of these mid-grade technologies change substantially depending on the scenario, particularly when prioritizing TRL or the lifespan of technologies. This variation implies that, while they may not be top-tier solutions, they do have potential advantages in certain applications. The mid-grade technologies, though not as consistently strong, show promise depending on the application and criteria prioritized. Eventually, the overall consistency of the rankings across different scenarios underscores the robustness of the evaluation, affirming that the leading technologies remain almost optimal for all choices even as specific priorities shift.

Conclusion

Since industries all over the world face the need to transition to sustainable energy systems, identifying the most appropriate power-to-heat technology becomes critical. This study contributes to this endeavour by conducting a thorough review and classification of ten technologies utilizing an MCDA framework and a rigorous scenario analysis. The findings of this study are especially useful for policy-makers, industry stakeholders, and researchers seeking to make informed choices that are in line with environmental sustainability goals. This study emphasizes the significance of identifying and classifying power-to-heat technologies and assessment criteria using an in-depth review of academic articles and industry reports. By collecting data from many sources in a methodical manner, the research assures that the chosen technologies and criteria are relevant and represent the most cutting-edge developments. In addition, by integrating the natural connections between the evaluation criteria, the analysis offers a more nuanced understanding of each technology's strengths, leading to a more cohesive and insightful framework for decision-making. This initial stage serves as a strong foundation for the future MCDA, ensuring that the evaluation is based on a complete awareness of the present technical landscape. The summary of the critical results is represented as follows:

- The methodology section outlines the systematic method used to evaluate alternatives, including criterion selection, WSM and TOPSIS aggregations, and weight distribution based on industry relevance. This rigorous method allowed for a clear, subjective comparison of alternatives, resulting in an extensive investigation that evaluated both quantitative and qualitative aspects of each criterion.
- The results demonstrate that Heat Pump and MVR surpass other technologies in a variety of categories, proving their durability, efficiency, and minimal environmental impact. These technologies appear as the most promising solutions for industrial applications, with substantial potential for lowering carbon footprints while retaining high operational effectiveness.
- The scenario analysis highlights the versatility and durability of Heat Pump and MVR technologies across various prioritizing situations, reinforcing their position as leading solutions for power-to-heat applications. Plasma Technology and EAFs, on the other hand, regularly score lower, indicating that they may require more research or are better suited for specialized applications where particular requirements are less important.
- The identical outcomes for most of the technologies across all scenarios underscore the robustness of the decision-making process, indicating that the ranking and evaluation of the technologies remain consistent regardless of which criterion is prioritized. This consistency highlights the reliability of the selected technologies, suggesting that the decision is well-supported by a comprehensive assessment and is unlikely to be influenced by shifts in weighing different factors. As a result, the chosen technologies can be confidently regarded as optimal solutions for the given objectives.

Finally, the suggested application of MCDA and scenario analysis in

a) Equal weighting

b) Electrification Stage

c) Efficiency/COP

d) Technology readiness level

e) Installation complexity

f) Carbon emission reduction

g) Lifespan

Fig. 8. Scenario analysis.

Fig. 9. Overview of scenario analysis.

this study indicates how beneficial these techniques are for guiding technology selection. Decision-makers can ensure that the chosen technologies are not only successful under present conditions but also robust to future changes in priorities and industry demands, by taking into account different criteria and prospective situations. This strategy helps to make more sustainable and informed decisions transitioning to a low-carbon industrial future.

Future works

While this study makes significant contributions to the identification and classification of power-to-heat technologies, project and site-specific aspects were not addressed. These characteristics can vary among industries and determine the most appropriate technology selection. Future case study research can build on this by adjusting the framework to specific industries, making it more applicable in a variety of contexts.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Arman Ashabi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mohamed Mostafa:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Andriy Hryshchenko:** Supervision. **Ken Bruton:** Supervision. **Dominic T.J. O’sullivan:** Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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